

CORRELATION OF LEVELS OF FOLATE, VITAMIN B₁₂, HEPCIDIN, AND SOME IRON INDICES WITH ANTHROPOMETRIC PARAMETERS IN TYPE-2-DIABETIC AND NON-DIABETIC SUBJECTS.

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Abstract

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a complex metabolic disorder frequently associated with iron and other micronutrient metabolism dysregulation. Anthropometric parameters, such as body mass index (BMI), waist circumference and hip circumference, may influence some micronutrients and iron indices through adiposity-related metabolic disturbances. This study evaluated the relationship between anthropometric indices and vitamin B₁₂, folate and selected iron indices (hepcidin, ferritin, serum iron, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), transferrin saturation (TSAT) and transferrin) among individuals with T2DM at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH), Nnewi, Nigeria. A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 80 subjects with type 2 diabetes and 80 age- and sex-matched non-diabetic controls. Anthropometric parameters including height, weight, body mass index (BMI), waist circumference and hip circumference were measured using standard procedures. Serum levels of vitamin B₁₂, folate, hepcidin, ferritin, iron, TIBC and transferrin were analyzed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay and spectrophotometric methods. Data were

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analyzed using Pearson's correlation and independent t-tests, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. The findings showed that the mean BMI, weight and waist circumference were significantly higher in the diabetic group than in the non-diabetic group (controls) ($P < 0.001$ respectively). A significant weak positive correlation was observed between BMI and transferrin among the non-diabetic subjects ($P = 0.022$) but not among the diabetic group. However, no significant correlation was observed between BMI and other parameters in the diabetic and non-diabetic groups ($P > 0.05$). Similarly, no significant correlation was observed between waist circumference and vitamin B₁₂, folate, hepcidin and other iron indices ($P > 0.05$). This study has identified that diabetic subjects exhibited significantly higher measures of adiposity compared to controls and anthropometric indices showed no significant correlation with hepcidin or iron status markers. These findings imply that iron dysregulation in T2DM may be influenced more by factors other than body composition.

Introduction

Diabetes is a disease that affects hundreds of millions of people worldwide. The prevalence of diabetes continues to rise, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, due to rapid urbanization and lifestyle changes (International Diabetes Federation, 2025). Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a long-standing and heterogeneous metabolic disease marked by sustained hyperglycemia arising from defective insulin secretion, insulin resistance or a combination of both (Goyal *et al.*, 2025). It is one of the most common non-communicable diseases worldwide and a major cause of morbidity and mortality. Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa are experiencing an unprecedented surge in the incidence of diabetes due to physical inactivity, unhealthy dietary habits and rising incidence of obesity (Olamoyegun *et al.*, 2024). The hallmark of T2DM is altered glucose metabolism, but the disease also exerts profound effects on lipid, protein and micronutrient metabolism. Iron has attracted increasing attention among the affected micronutrients due to its potential bidirectional relationship with insulin resistance, oxidative stress and inflammation (Ambachew and Biadgo, 2017). Anthropometrically, obesity and adiposity are major risk factors for insulin resistance and T2DM (Bellou *et al.*, 2018). Hepcidin levels are elevated in patients with obesity and central adiposity, even in the absence of overt iron overload. Increased serum hepcidin and inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein have been observed in women with greater central fat distribution, together with impaired iron metabolism, which is attributed to inflammation-induced hepcidin synthesis (Stoffel *et al.*, 2020). Clinical studies also indicate alterations in hepcidin, iron indices and other micronutrients in individuals with obesity and obesity-related T2DM (Siemonsma *et al.*, 2024). Anthropometric measurements, such as body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (WC), hip circumference (HC) and waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), are widely used indicators of general and central obesity. These indices serve not only as fat distribution markers but also as surrogate markers of metabolic risk (Aguh *et al.*, 2021; Purohit and Tiwari, 2014). Among them, waist circumference and Waist-hip-ratio (WHR) are particularly important for assessing visceral fat accumulation, which is more metabolically active and inflammatory than subcutaneous fat.

Several studies have investigated the association between anthropometric indices, iron indices and other micronutrients in diabetic populations, with varying outcomes. Visceral adiposity and abdominal-to-gluteal fat ratio have been shown to be positively correlated with serum ferritin and iron levels in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus, suggesting that body fat distribution may influence systemic iron metabolism (Zimiao *et al.*, 2022). Conversely, some studies have reported no significant associations between BMI or waist circumference and iron indices after controlling for inflammatory markers, suggesting that inflammatory pathways rather than adiposity may mediate the observed relationships (Harrison *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, increased serum ferritin levels in individuals with higher body mass index (BMI) or central obesity have been linked to insulin resistance and poor glycemic control in type 2 diabetes mellitus (Khyber *et al.*, 2024). However, elevated ferritin levels may not reflect true iron overload but rather increased inflammatory activity and altered iron compartmentalization. Likewise, reductions in transferrin saturation (TSAT) and increase in total iron binding capacity (TIBC) among obese individuals with type 2 diabetes may indicate decreased circulating iron despite adequate body stores (Vaquero *et al.*, 2021).

Despite extensive global research, there remains a paucity of data exploring the interrelationships between anthropometric indices, vitamin B₁₂, folate, hepcidin and iron indices in African populations, particularly among Nigerian diabetics. Given the increasing prevalence of obesity and T2DM in Nigeria, understanding these relationships is of great clinical and public health relevance. Therefore, this study was designed to assess the correlation between anthropometric indices (BMI, waist circumference and hip circumference) and vitamin B₁₂, folic acid and iron metabolism markers (hepcidin, ferritin, and serum iron, transferrin, total iron-binding capacity and transferrin saturation) among individuals with T2DM. By examining these relationships, this study aims to clarify whether adiposity and body composition influence the regulation of these parameters in diabetics. A better understanding of these interactions may inform more comprehensive strategies for managing metabolic and other complications in Nigerian diabetic populations.

Materials and Methods

Study Site

This study was conducted at the Endocrinology, Diabetes and Metabolism Unit of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Anambra State, South-Eastern Nigeria. The hospital is a tertiary institution owned by the federal government that provides health care services to residents of the state and beyond. It runs a diabetic clinic that attends to patients from within and surrounding states.

Study Design

This was a hospital-based, cross-sectional study designed to correlate the levels of folic acid, vitamin B₁₂, hepcidin and some iron indices with anthropometric parameters in type-2-diabetic and non-diabetic subjects. The study population included patients with diabetes attending the clinic as test subjects and non-diabetic subjects as control subjects.

Determination of Sample Size

The total sample size of subjects for this study was determined using the following formula:

$$N = Z^2 P (1-P) / d^2 \text{ (Naing et al., 2006).}$$

Where N = Desired Sample Size

Z = standard deviation at 99% confidence interval, which is 1.96

P = 4.6% prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus in South East Nigeria = 0.046 (Uloko *et al.*, 2018)

d = degree of precision = 0.05

Therefore:

$$N = 1.96^2 \times 0.046 (1-0.046) / 0.05^2$$

$$= \frac{0.177 \times 0.95}{0.0025} = 67.26$$

From the calculation, the sample size is 67.

Thus, the minimum sample size was rounded to 80.

Study Participants

The study included 160 participants comprising 80 patients with diagnosed T2DM attending the endocrinology clinic and 80 age- and sex-matched healthy non-diabetic controls.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria included adult patients with T2DM aged 20–60 years on stable management without acute complications.

Subjects with anemia from non-diabetic causes, those with infectious or chronic diseases such as liver disease, HIV, tuberculosis, severe malaria, malignancies and renal diseases, those who received blood transfusions in the previous 3 months and those on hematinics, supplements and other medications that interfere with iron were excluded.

Ethical consideration and Informed consent

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi. Informed consent was obtained from each participant before recruitment into the study.

Anthropometric Measurements

Height and weight were measured using a stadiometer and digital scale. Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight (kg)/height² (m²). The waist and hip circumferences were measured using a non-stretchable measuring tape.

Sample Collection

Venous blood (5 mL) was aseptically collected from each participant via standard venipuncture into plain (serum) sample bottles. Blood samples were allowed to clot at room temperature and subsequently centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 10 min to obtain serum. The separated serum was carefully aliquoted into clean, labeled tubes and stored frozen at -20°C until analysis to prevent degradation of analytes.

Laboratory Analysis

Quantitative Determination of Hepcidin using the Sandwich-ELISA method

The wells for the diluted standard, blank and sample are determined. Then 100µL each dilution of the standard, blank and sample was added to the appropriate wells. All samples and standards were assayed in duplicate. The plate was covered with the sealer provided in the kit and incubated at 37°C for 90 min at 37°C. Solutions were added to the bottom of the micro ELISA well. The liquid from each well was decanted and 100µL of Biotinylated Detection Ab working solution was added immediately to each well and the plate was covered with a new sealer and then incubated at 37°C for 1 hour. The solution from each well was decanted and 350µL of wash buffer was added to each well. This was soaked for 1-2 minutes and after which the solution was aspirated or decanted from each well and patted dry against clean absorbent paper. This wash step was repeated 3 times after which 100µL of HRP conjugate working solution was added to each well and the plate was covered with a new sealer and incubated for 30 min at 37°C. The supernatant from each well was decanted and the washing process was repeated 5 times. Then 90µL of Substrate Reagent was added to each well. The plate was covered with a new sealer and incubated at 37°C for approximately 15 min while being protected from

light. Afterwards, 50 μ L of Stop Solution was added to each well, and the OD value of each well was determined at once with a microplate reader set to 450 nm.

Quantitative Determination of Vitamin B₁₂ using Competitive ELISA

All reagents and samples were brought to room temperature and mixed thoroughly by gently swirling before use. Fifty microliters (50 μ L) of standard, blank or sample was added per well. The blank well was added with the reference, standard and sample diluent. Then 50 μ L of Biotinylated Detection Ab working solution was immediately added to each well and covered with the provided plate sealer. The plate was gently tapped to ensure thorough mixing and incubated at 37°C for 45 min. Each well was aspirated and washed with wash buffer (approximately 350 μ L) and the process was repeated three times. After the last wash, any remaining wash buffer was removed by aspirating or decanting and the plate was inverted and patted against a thick, clean, absorbent paper. Then 100 μ L of HRP Conjugate working solution was added to each well, covered with a new plate sealer and incubated for 30 min at 37°C. The aspiration/wash process was repeated for five times and 90 μ L of Substrate Solution was added to each well and covered with a new plate sealer. This was incubated and protected from sunlight for approximately 15 min at 37°C. Afterwards, 50 μ L of Stop Solution was added to each well and the color immediately turned yellow. The OD value of each well was determined at once using a microplate reader set to 450 nm.

Quantitative Determination of Folate Concentration (ACCU-BIND) using Competitive Binding Protein assay method

The wash buffer was diluted to 1000 ml with distilled or deionized water. An aliquot of stabilizing agent was added to prepare 1/40 (stabilizing agent/releasing agent) dilute solution and sufficient test tubes were obtained for the preparation of all patient samples, controls and calibrator.

Then 0.10ml (100 μ L) of all samples was dispensed into individual test tubes. Furthermore, 0.050ml (50 μ L) of the prepared extraction agent was pipetted into each tube and shaken. This was allowed to stand for 15 min, after which 0.050ml (50 μ L) of the neutralizing buffer was added and mixed and allowed to stand for an additional 5 min before dispensing into the microwells. The microplate well for calibrator, control and patient specimen was formatted in duplicate and 0.050ml (50 μ L) of the appropriate extracted folate calibrator, control or specimen was pipetted into the assigned well. Then 0.050ml (50 μ L) of Folate Enzyme Reagents was added to all the wells and the microplate was mixed gently for 20-30 seconds. After which 0.050ml (50 μ L) of the Folate Biotin Reagent was added to all the wells and the microplate was gently mixed again for 20-30 seconds. The microplate was covered and incubated at room temperature for 45 minutes. The supernatant was decanted and 0.350ml (350 μ L) of wash buffer was added to each well. This step was repeated for additional 3 times and then 0.100ml (100 μ L) of the substrate reagent was added to all wells and incubated at room temperature for twenty minutes and 0.050ml (50 μ L) of stop solution was added to each well and gently mixed for 15-20seconds. The absorbance in each well was then read at 450 nm using a reference wavelength of 620-630 nm.

Quantitative Determination of the Total Iron/Total Iron Binding Capacity

Serum Iron

Test tubes were labeled "Blank," "Standard," "Control" and "Sample," respectively and 2.5 ml of iron buffer reagent was added to each tube. Then 0.5 ml (500 μ L) of the sample was added to the respective tubes and mixed. While 500 μ L iron-free water (500 L) was added to the blank, after which the spectrophotometer was zeroed at 560 nm with the reagent blank to read and record the absorbances of all tubes (A1 reading). After the first reading, 0.05 ml (50 μ L) of the iron color reagent was added to all the tubes. All the tubes were mixed and placed in a heating bath at 37°C for 10 min. Then, the spectrophotometer is zeroed at 560 nm with the blank

reagent. (Wavelength range: 520-560 nm) to finally read and record the absorbances of all the tubes (A2 reading).

Calculation

$$\text{Total iron (ug/dL)} = \frac{A2 \text{ Test} - A1 \text{ Test}}{A2 \text{ Std} - A1 \text{ Std}} \times \text{Concentration of Std}$$

Where A = absorbance and Std = standard

Unsaturated Iron Binding Capacity (UIBC)

Test tubes were labeled "Blank", "Standard", "Control" and "Test" and 2.0 ml UIBC buffer reagent was added to all tubes. Then, 1.0 ml of iron-free water was added to the blank and mixed. Then 0.5 ml (500 µl) of iron-free water plus 0.5 ml (500 µl) of the standard were added to the standard and mixed, while 0.5 ml (500 µl) of the respective sample plus 0.5 ml (500 µl) of the iron standard were added to 'Test' and mixed. The spectrophotometer was then zeroed at 560 nm with a blank reagent and the absorbance of all tubes (A1 reading) was read. Then 0.05 ml (50 µl) of iron color reagent was added to all tubes and mixed. Then all tubes were placed in a heating bath at 37°C for 10 min. The spectrophotometer was then zeroed at 560 nm with a blank reagent and the absorbance of all tubes (A2 reading) was read and recorded.

Calculation

$$\text{UIBC (ug/dL)} = \text{concentration of std} - \left(\frac{A2 \text{ Test} - A1 \text{ Test}}{A2 \text{ Std} - A1 \text{ Std}} \right) \times \text{Concentration of Std}$$

$$\text{TIBC (µg/dl)} = \text{serum iron level} + \text{UIBC}$$

Quantitative Determination of Ferritin Concentration by a Colorimetric Microplate Enzyme Immunoassay

The microplate wells were formatted in duplicate for each serum standard, control and patient specimen. Unused microwell strips were stored at 2-8°C. Next, 25µl of the appropriate serum standard control or specimen was pipetted into the assigned well, followed by adding 100µl of the Ferritin Biotin Reagent to each well, ensuring that all reagents were dispensed close to the bottom of the coated well. The microplate was gently swirled for 20-30 seconds to mix and cover and then incubated at room temperature for 30 min. After incubation, the contents of the microplate were discarded by decantation and the wells were washed three times with 350µl of wash buffer. Subsequently, 100µl of the Ferritin Enzyme Conjugate was added to each well without shaking the plate. The microplate was incubated again for 30 min at room temperature before discarding the microplate contents and repeating the washing steps. Next, 100µl of working substrate solution was added to all wells without shaking the plate, followed by incubation at room temperature for 15 min. Finally, 50µl of stop solution was added to each well, mixed gently, and the absorbance in each well was read at 450 nm using a microplate reader within 30 min of adding the stop solution.

Quantitative Determination of Transferrin using the Sandwich ELISA method

All samples and standards were assayed in duplicate. The Standards and the test sample(s) were loaded into the ELISA wells as quickly as possible to avoid a shift in optical density readings. The use of a multichannel pipette reduces this occurrence. Then 100 µL of Standard 0 (0.0 ng/mL), Standard 1 (9.38 ng/mL), Standard 2 (18.75 ng/mL), Standard 3 (37.50 ng/mL), Standard 4 (75 ng/mL), Standard 5 (150 ng/mL), Standard 6 (300 ng/mL) and Standard 7 (600 ng/mL) were pipetted in duplicate. Also 100-µL sample was pipetted (in duplicate) into the pre-designated wells. The microtiter plate was incubated at room temperature for 30 min. The plate was kept covered and level during incubation. The contents of the wells are aspirated following incubation. Each well was completely filled with an appropriately diluted wash solution and aspirated. This process was repeated three times for a total of four washes. Then 100 µL of appropriately diluted Enzyme-Antibody Conjugate was pipetted into each well. Plates were incubated at room temperature for 30 min. The plate was kept covered in

the dark and level during incubation. The wells were washed and blotted as described in Steps 5/6. 100 μ L of TMB Substrate Solution was pipetted into each well. Plates were incubated in the dark at room temperature for precisely 10 min. After 10 min, 100 μ L of Stop Solution was added to each well. The absorbance (450 nm) of each well was determined within 30 min. The plate reader was calibrated according to the manufacturer's specifications.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26.0. Continuous variables are expressed as mean \pm SD. Group comparisons were made using independent t-tests, and Pearson's correlation was used to assess the relationship between variables. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The mean weight, BMI and waist circumference were significantly higher in the diabetic group than in the non-diabetic group (controls) ($P < 0.001$ respectively). However, no significant difference was observed in the mean height and hip circumference between the test and control groups ($P > 0.05$) (Table 1).

A significant weak positive correlation was observed between BMI and transferrin levels among the non-diabetic subjects ($P = 0.022$) but not among the diabetic group. However, no significant correlation was observed between BMI and other parameters in the diabetic and non-diabetic groups ($P > 0.05$) (Table 2).

No significant correlation was found between waist circumference and vitamin B12, folate, hepcidin and other iron indices ($P > 0.05$). Similarly, no significant difference was found between hip circumference and vitamin B12, folate, hepcidin and other iron indices ($P > 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 1: Mean values of some anthropometric variables in the diabetic and non-diabetic groups (Mean \pm SD)

Parameters	Diabetic subjects	Non-diabetic subjects	t-test	p-value
Height (m)	1.6885 \pm 0.08	1.6523 \pm 0.09	-1.914	0.059
Weight (kg)	76.400 \pm 10.36	67.755 \pm 11.08	-3.734	<0.001 *
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.775 \pm 2.85	24.626 \pm 3.18	-4.868	<0.001 *
Waist circumference (cm)	96.88 \pm 17.92	81.62 \pm 9.19	-5.104	<0.001 *
Hip circumference (cm)	99.70 \pm 6.13	99.28 \pm 5.42	-0.342	0.733

Key

* $p < 0.05$ = significant;

BMI = body mass index

Table 2: Correlation of BMI with Hcpidin, Folate, Vitamin B₁₂ and Iron indices in the diabetic and non-diabetic (control) groups

Parameters	Diabetic		Non-diabetic	
	r-value	P-value	r-value	P-value
BMI versus Ferritin	-0.091	0.576	-0.044	0.769
BMI versus Vit B₁₂	-0.065	0.692	0.026	0.865
BMI versus hepcidin	0.171	0.292	0.035	0.814
BMI versus Folate	-0.032	0.845	-0.015	0.922
BMI versus iron	-0.112	0.493	-0.087	0.559
BMI versus TIBC	0.082	0.615	0.285	0.052
BMI versus TSAT	-0.101	0.533	-0.169	0.257
BMI versus transferrin	0.124	0.445	0.334	0.022*

Key: * p<0.05 is significant.

BMI = body mass index,

TIBC = total iron binding capacity,

VitB₁₂ = vitamin B₁₂

TSAT = transferrin saturation

WC = waist circumference

HC = Hip circumference

Table 3: Correlation of waist and hip circumference with Hcpidin, Folate, Vit B₁₂ and Iron indices in the diabetic and non-diabetic (control) groups

Parameters	Diabetic		Non-diabetic	
	r-value	P-value	r-value	P-value
WC vs. Ferritin	-0.200	0.216	-0.076	0.612
WC vs. Vit B₁₂	-0.137	0.401	0.071	0.636
WC vs. hepcidin	0.007	0.965	0.107	0.475
WC vs. Folate	0.208	0.197	0.036	0.809
WC vs. iron	0.307	0.054	-0.078	0.603
WC vs. TIBC	-0.077	0.638	-0.062	0.679
WC vs. TSAT	0.268	0.094	-0.013	0.932
WC vs. transferrin	-0.227	0.159	0.015	0.918
HC vs. Ferritin	-0.165	0.310	-0.008	0.958
HC vs. Vit B₁₂	-0.151	0.351	-0.075	0.616

HC vs. hepcidin	0.137	0.398	-0.066	0.659
HC vs. Folate	-0.045	0.780	-0.135	0.365
HC vs. iron	0.300	0.060	0.112	0.452
HC vs. TIBC	-0.120	0.460	0.196	0.186
HC vs. TSAT	0.274	0.087	0.033	0.824
HC vs. transferrin	-0.258	0.111	0.073	0.627

BMI = body mass index,

TIBC = total iron binding capacity,

VitaminB₁₂ = VitaminB₁₂

TSAT = transferrin saturation

WC = waist circumference

HC = Hip circumference

Discussion

This study investigated the relationships between anthropometric indices and vitamin B₁₂, folate and iron metabolism markers, including hepcidin, ferritin, serum iron, transferrin, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC) and transferrin saturation (TSAT), in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and non-diabetic control subjects. The findings of the study revealed that diabetic subjects had significantly higher body mass index, weight and waist circumference than non-diabetic controls. These findings are consistent with the widely hypothesized association between T2DM and central adiposity, which predisposes patients with T2DM to insulin resistance, chronic inflammation and metabolic dysregulation (Bellou *et al.*, 2018; Olamoyegun *et al.*, 2024). The significant elevations in BMI and waist circumference among diabetic subjects in this study highlight the ongoing challenge of obesity in the Nigerian population and its contribution to T2DM pathophysiology. Central adiposity is particularly important because visceral fat is metabolically active and releases pro-inflammatory adipokines, including tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), which can exacerbate insulin resistance and potentially influence iron metabolism (Kirichenko *et al.*, 2022; Gupta *et al.*, 2023). These biochemical mediators may also stimulate hepatic hepcidin expression via the IL-6/JAK-STAT3 signaling pathway, thereby promoting iron sequestration and functional iron deficiency (Stoffel *et al.*, 2020; Nemeth and Ganz, 2023).

Correlational analyses between anthropometric indices and Vitamin B₁₂, Folate, Iron metabolism markers in our study revealed non-significant relationships. This implies that while anthropometric indices reflect overall and central adiposity, they may not serve as strong independent determinants of systemic iron metabolism and changes in vitamin B₁₂ and Folate. Therefore, our findings may be interpreted to mean that in Nigerian diabetics, anthropometric indices do not directly predict the levels of these parameters. This may reflect population-specific factors, such as differences in genetic variants of regulatory genes or the variable influence of inflammatory cytokines (Gichohi-Wainaina *et al.*, 2016; Siemonsma *et al.*, 2024). The lack of statistically significant correlations between anthropometric measures and iron indices aligns with previous reports indicating that the relationship between obesity and iron metabolism may be mediated primarily through inflammatory pathways rather than direct effects of body fat (Harrison *et al.*, 2023).

Comparisons with previous studies in other populations reveal interesting differences. Central obesity has been consistently associated with elevated hepcidin and ferritin levels in Western cohorts, whereas our study in a Nigerian cohort did not demonstrate a statistically significant relationship. This discrepancy may be attributable

to differences in dietary intake, chronic infection burden, genetic background or environmental exposures, highlighting the importance of conducting population-specific investigations (Harrison *et al.*, 2023).

Limitations of the Study

Despite this study's strengths, some limitations must be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference; longitudinal studies are required to determine the temporal relationships between obesity, vitamin B₁₂, folate, hepcidin and iron indices. Second, inflammatory markers were not measured in parallel with iron indices, which could have provided additional insight into the mediating role of inflammation. Third, dietary iron intake and micronutrient status, which may influence circulating iron parameters, were not assessed. Future studies incorporating these variables along with genetic profiling and larger sample sizes could provide more definitive conclusions. Furthermore, the study was conducted at a single tertiary health facility, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other Nigerian populations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present study demonstrates that while diabetic subjects in this Nigerian cohort exhibited higher BMI, weight, and waist circumference, these anthropometric measures were not significantly associated with vitamin B₁₂, folate and iron indices, including hepcidin and ferritin. These findings imply that adiposity does not directly predict iron dysregulation and the levels of these parameters in T2DM.

Recommendations

The population-specific differences observed in this study highlight the importance of conducting localized research to inform targeted interventions aimed at mitigating metabolic and other diabetes complications in Nigeria. Further longitudinal studies incorporating inflammatory markers, dietary iron assessment and genetic factors are recommended to elucidate the mechanisms linking adiposity and iron metabolism in Nigerian populations.

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